

Political Participation of Indigenous Koch Community in Gazipur District: A Review of Literature

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Abstract

From the creation of the universe, people of different ethnic groups have been living in the world. There are about three million indigenous people living in 35 districts including three hill districts of Bangladesh. Koch Indigenous people came in Gazipur district, Bangladesh approximately in the beginning of 7th century and live in the plains of north and north-eastern region of Dhaka division. Despite the active participation of the indigenous people in the war of independence, the issue of fundamental rights and constitutional recognition of these small groups has been neglected since the independence of the country. They are far behind in terms of political participation in Bangladesh. The Koch indigenous people has absolutely very limited participation in local and national politics. Their political participation is limited only to the active voting process in national and local elections. In the context of above, I have tried to do research work on this issue. The general objective of the study is to learn the political participation of Koch communities in Gazipur District, Bangladesh. The study was based on secondary sources of data like-journal, article, newspaper, conference, seminar and books. The crisis of the political identity of the indigenous has been historically recognized. The findings of the study most of the Koch indigenous people are deprived of socially, economically and politically just civil status and fundamental rights.

Keywords: Political Participation, Indigenous, Koch Community, Fundamental Rights, Bangladesh

Introduction:

Bangladesh is a communal harmony country along with the majority Bengali population. There are various small ethnic groups. That is why Bangladesh is called a country of cultural and ethnic diversity about 54 or more indigenous people speak at least 35 languages. Currently, the population of the country is about 16, 50, 478, which is about 1% of the total population of the country. This is according to the last census of the year 2022 (BBS, 2022). However, they claim their total population to be about four (4) million (Barkat, 2015). Some indigenous live in the Chittagong hill tracts, but most of the indigenous live in the plains. Chakma, Marma, Rakhaine, Murong live in the hilly areas and Santal, Garo, Manipuri and Koch indigenous live in the plains. Koch is an important indigenous among them. From the war of independence their constitutional and political rights are very much neglected by the majority Bengali people. Political participation of Koch community in Gazipur district is a significant issue for good reason. Politics and participation convictions are deeply related to each other. Because without peoples' participation, political system cannot survive in a democratic country like-Bangladesh. Not only in Bangladesh but also in any democratic countries in the world, citizen participation continuous to play a great role. People's participation in national politics creates an opportunity to build a prosperous state if this method is applied by the prevailing culture (Yongmin, 2006). Sometimes political instability created by rolling political parties or opposition political parties in national politics can bring forward unconventional participation in politics. However, political stability at the national level is essential for participation in politics. The modern state consists of a

small number of individuals who issue and execute orders intended to influence a large number, including themselves (Laski, 1925).

All citizens are obliged to obey the orders of the government within the settled area: its inconsistency can sometimes be noticed. Therefore, without political participation, the right people at the right time cannot be elected. It is very necessary for national interest and sovereignty. Political participation at the national level is undeniable to protect national interests and sovereignty from foreign threats, and aggression (Yongmin, 2013). In 1971, Bangladesh became independent by defeating the Pakistani invaders by fighting wittedly and losing their fresh virginity. Despite this self-sacrifice, it was not possible to achieve the real goal level including stability in national or local politics. Common people have been deeply involved in politics is concerned with the head of government, the legislature and the government ([http://Ivythesis, typepad.com](http://Ivythesis.typepad.com), 2008). Power and politics are related to the now. In general, Power is the control of one person over the wind and actions of another person. But the relationship between the common people and the right of control and authority of the people is called political power (Morgen thau, 1964). There is a psychological connection between those on whom it is applied and those who practice it.

The aim of the political party is to acquire the power of the state in a legitimate way. It is not possible for any person or organization to reach power without the direct or indirect political participation of the common people. John Locke in his famous book “Two Treatises of civil government” said that, the common people alone are the source of all power (Ahmad, 1994). That is why Aristotle says that, the majority of people have sovereign power and those who are free but not rich (Shultz, 2003). By participating in politics common people can form political parties and become national leaders. Representations of political parties participating in a parliamentary democracy use their voting power to regulate government activities and protect public interests. Forming political parties under the leadership of common people, expanding the path of political education, protecting democracy, stopping the path of dictatorial government forever, building positive public opinion and establishing national unity. Greater political participation is an important right of national politics. In fact, there is no substitute for right if a person is to reach the social optimum. Every modern democratic state should provide this right in the larger interest of the nation. Ensuring brotherhood, tolerance, acceptance, solidarity, accountability throughout the country is possible only through positive political participation. The basic foundation of a democratic government is the active participation of citizens in its every process.

Objectives of the study:

The general objective of the study is to learn the political participation of the Koch community in Gazipur district, Bangladesh.

Specific Objectives:

1. To learn the profile of the Koch community in Gazipur district.
2. To explore how the Koch community participate in politics.
3. To investigate the challenges faced by the Koch community in terms of political participation.

Methodology

The present study was based on secondary sources of data. The following tools and methods were used to collect data for the study. Journal articles, newspaper articles, books, internet, Facebook newsfeed, abstract books, presented conference papers, documentaries, key note papers, seminar and workshop papers.

Review of literature

In this section it has been reviewed the relevant literature.

Siddique, et al., (2014). discusses “Political Participation of Ethnic Minority Groups in Bangladesh: A Case Study on Santal Community”. This research primarily employs a quantitative approach and utilizes a survey to gather data from participants. Additionally, the study incorporated qualitative methods as well. The findings indicate that nearly all respondents within the community, spanning various education and occupation categories, consistently participate in both national and local elections, as well as engage actively in electoral meetings, rallies, and campaigning efforts. The study concludes that the Santal community does not show indifference toward political engagement, with their participation levels being commendable when compared to other ethnic groups in Bangladesh, such as the Garos, Hazong, and Oran communities.

Siddique., (2018). “Electoral Participation of indigenous people in Bangladesh: A case study on the Garo community”. This study aims and identifies the level of electoral participation of Garo people in the 9th parliamentary election in Bangladesh. This research primarily utilizes a quantitative approach. The data collection involved both secondary and primary sources. Additionally, an observational method was employed for this study. It was found that nearly all members of the community actively participate in various elections. They exhibit awareness and a sense of responsibility regarding their voting rights, similar to the general population of Bengali people. The research ultimately concludes that the Garo community actively took part in the 9th parliamentary election, demonstrating a satisfactory level of participation.

Khan., (2012). “Nature of the political participations of the oraon community of Barind in Bangladesh”. The present research aims to explore the political involvement of the Oraon community in Barind, Bangladesh. This study employed both qualitative and quantitative approaches. It is noteworthy that the political engagement of the Oraon community surpasses that of other communities. The political participation of Oraon women is superior to that of Oraon men, and all members adhere to electoral conduct, with none of them breaching election regulations.

Hossain, M.R.R., et al., (2017). “Peoples voting behavior in local election: A study on Anandanagar union parishad, Pirgacha, Rangpur”. The aim of this research is to explore the reasons why some citizens participate in voting while others abstain as well as to examine the socio-economic and political factors that influence the voting habits of the local population. While this study is predominantly qualitative, it also employs quantitative methods to enhance clarity. Interviews were conducted using both open-ended and closed-ended questions. The findings indicate that voting turnout varies based on age, gender, and education level. Younger and middle-aged individuals are more likely to participate in voting compared to older individuals. Female voters are less motivated to vote than their male counterparts, while illiterate voters show more interest in participating than educated voters, as their voting decisions are primarily influenced by perceived benefits rather than considerations regarding the electoral process or candidates' qualifications.

Rashiduzzaman, et al., (2022). “Voting behavior of Santal tribal community: A case study on Deopara union of Godagari upazila, Rajshahi, Bangladesh.” The research aims to explore the voting behavior of the Santal tribal community in Bangladesh. This research primarily employs a qualitative survey methodology. The Santal people lack awareness regarding their rights and do not fully understand how to exercise their voting rights. When it comes to voting, women's decisions are often swayed by their husbands or fathers, reflecting a lingering patriarchal influence in the electoral process. Such notions continue to persist among the Santal community to this day.

Morium, B., (2024). “People’s political participation: A theoretical exposition and reality in case of Bangladesh”. The research has been carried out to explore the motivations behind individuals' engagement in parliamentary democracy in Bangladesh. This investigation relies on empirical research that utilizes a qualitative approach. While the data is presented in a quantitative format and some descriptive statistics are applied for analysis, no causal relationships or statistical significance are identified in this study. The result of the study shows that most people participate in politics only for the country and choose their preferred party and candidate first in voting. They generally do not vote outside the party.

Arrese, D., (2020). “The Right of Political Participation of Indigenous People and the UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples” discusses the responsibilities that the international legal framework

regarding the rights of indigenous peoples places on States in relation to political participation, particularly the 2007 UN Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP). This article centers on one specific aspect of political participation. It asserts that the effectiveness of each method cannot be judged in isolation but should be evaluated in relation to the particular context where a specific method is implemented. Most critically, the success of any particular method should be assessed based on how well it enables indigenous communities to genuinely influence political decision-making, especially in matters that directly impact them.

Raghavendra, S., (2024). *Has analyzed "Political Participation of Tribals in India: A systematic approach"*. This research aims to promote a more inclusive and fair political environment that meets the diverse aspirations and needs of the tribal population in India. He also examines the key factors influencing the political involvement of tribal communities while exploring the challenges and opportunities they face within the Indian political landscape. The research methodology utilized in this study is based on reviewing existing literature, analyzing case studies, and examining empirical data to provide a historical context and evaluate the political engagement of tribes in India. The findings of this study are

intended to deepen the understanding of tribal political participation in India and offer valuable insights for policymakers, researchers, and activists dedicated to enhancing the political empowerment of tribal groups.

Sangma, B.M., (2023). *"Electoral participation of Garo tribes in Meghalaya: A study of 2023 legislative assembly election,"* explores the factors that led to the significant electoral engagement of the Garo tribes in Meghalaya. It also examines the strong sense of community and identity among the Garo people, along with their high educational attainment. The research employs a descriptive and documentary analysis method, using qualitative data collected through interviews. The findings indicate that the 2023 legislative assembly election saw a notable voter turnout among Garo tribes, showcasing their dedication to the democratic process. The study also noted various political alliances and coalition formations aimed at addressing the needs of the Garo tribes. Additionally, there was a marked increase in the participation of Garo youth in the electoral process.

Sarowardy., (2000). In his dissertation titled *"People's Participation in Bangladesh Politics: A Study of June 1996 Parliamentary Elections"* has illustrated the nature and extent of public involvement in the political landscape of Bangladesh. This research was conducted to explore the variables and factors that influence people's participation, taking into account various influencing elements. The study also seeks to examine the public's awareness and their perceptions regarding politicians and the political system in general. Nevertheless, this research offers insight into the level of political engagement among the populace in Bangladesh.

Sobolewska, et.al., (2015). Discusses *"Understanding the effects of religious attendance on political participation among ethnic minorities of different religions."* They sought to explore the different factors related to attendance and its impact on political engagement among ethnic minorities. This research utilizes the 2010 Ethnic Minority British Election Study to conceptualize the connection between religious attendance and the political involvement of ethnic minorities within a European setting, while also expanding current theories to encompass non-Christian minority religions. The findings indicate that British minority churches and places of worship exhibit varying levels of willingness and effectiveness in politically inspiring their congregants, concluding that this is linked to the political significance of specific religions within the context of the United Kingdom.

Tantra, et al., (2019). *"Women's Political Participation in Bangladesh: Status Quo, Obstacles, and Future Prospects"*. Aimed to investigate the importance of women's involvement in parliament in the contemporary world. This research utilized a qualitative approach to explore the right to political participation for indigenous peoples, emphasizing how this right is grounded in international law, international human rights law, and international indigenous law (Tomaselli, 2017). The paper concludes with a demand from women in Bangladesh for increased participation in political activities.

Tamanna, M., (2018). *"The political perception of youth in Bangladesh."* The research focused on examining how young people are redefining the traditional notions of state authority and identifying the factors behind their lack of political involvement, which ultimately poses a challenge

to the political framework of Bangladesh. Both quantitative and qualitative approaches were utilized to address the research questions. Additionally, focus group discussions (FGD), in-depth interviews, and observations were carried out to collect information. The results of this study indicate that urban youth have a negative view of current political affairs and tend to steer clear of political engagement; there has been little research on how youth perceive politics. In Bangladesh, the youth demographic is not politically hopeless but rather disconnected. Security concerns hinder the younger generation's involvement in Bangladeshi politics. Additionally, many families rely solely on their youth members as breadwinners, making it difficult for them to concentrate on politics.

Banks., (2006). "Political participation and the urban poor in Dhaka city". The primary goal was to understand the following question: despite being the majority of the electorate, what barriers prevent the interests of the urban poor from receiving adequate attention, and whom do slum dwellers engage with to address their social issues or promote their interests? Additionally, the research sought to examine the steps taken to mobilize slum dwellers through the Basti Basheer Odhikar Surikha Committee (BOSC) program operated by a coalition for the urban poor. This study primarily utilizes qualitative methods, although quantitative methods have been applied in certain instances. Focus group discussions were conducted to gather more precise and logical insights into how failures in urban governance particularly affect the most vulnerable households, which experience social, economic, political, and cultural marginalization. Various factors such as low incomes, inadequate health, difficulty in finding employment, obstacles to accessing services, environmental threats and gender inequities all contribute to urban poverty.

Blair., (2000). Examined the concepts of participation and accountability within democratic local governance. His study covered six nations: Bolivia, Honduras, India, Mali, Philippines, and Ukraine. The research concludes that participation holds considerable promise for enhancing democratic local governance, although there are notable limitations.

Barman, B., (2021). A study on voting behavior: Specially focus on the area under Sarukhetri Development Block. To examine the major factors which are affecting voting behavior as well political behavior were the objectives of the study. The methodology used for this study is analytical. The collection of data for the study has been drawn from both primary and secondary sources of data collection. Several factors influence voter behavior, including religion, caste, community, language, money, policy or philosophy, polling purpose, extent of franchise, political wave and so on. These characteristics are used by political parties and groups in order to win the fight of the voting box.

Chicham., (2023). "Indigenous peoples of Bangladesh and their major problems and challenges" discusses the significant problems and challenges faced by indigenous people and to thoroughly analyze effective strategies for addressing these issues was the primary goal. The study primarily utilized a quantitative research method. Also all sub method of the qualitative method including face to face interview, record data, observation, discussions, analyze data. The indigenous people of Bangladesh face numerous challenges and problems in their daily lives. They are marginalized and often subjected to discrimination, poverty and lack of access to education, healthcare and employment opportunities. Their lands are being seized and their cultures, traditions are being threatened.

Rahman., (2023). "Assessing the political system in Bangladesh: Challenges and prospects for democratic consolidation". The goal of this article is to comparatively analyze evolution of political system of Bangladesh, its constitutional development, and politics, and address issues hampering functioning of democracy in the country. As a research method, both qualitative and quantitative methods have been used to estimate the unfavorable factors in the political system of Bangladesh. The investigation made in this research allows drawing a conclusion that the political order in Bangladesh is determined by historical factors as well as by political cleavages and electoral frauds are two of the bottlenecks that hinder democratic processes as well as confrontations politics and further lowness the prospects of political culture where democracy is adhered to.

Chakma., (2022). "Does political security matter? A study on the life satisfaction of indigenous peoples of the Chittagong Hill Tracts" deals with the new perspectives on how political insecurity, stemming from government oppression and systematic human rights violations, negatively impacts the life

satisfaction of indigenous communities in the Chittagong Hill Tracts (CHT). This investigation has explored the research question utilizing a survey data set (N=384) that includes various variables related to the political security and life satisfaction of indigenous populations in CHT, Bangladesh. The results of this study indicate that there is an adverse correlation between the infringement of basic freedoms and civil rights and overall life satisfaction.

Biswas, S., (2018). "State of indigenous people"s rights in Bangladesh: An analysis of bureaucratic and political sensitivity". The primary goal was to examine the constitutional rights of indigenous peoples in Bangladesh, along with the significant international human rights agreements ratified by the Bangladeshi government. Both the secondary and the primary data sources had been used. This study also emphasizes qualitative analysis to support the arguments, although it has used some rationale quantitative information in specific cases. The study revealed that many government policies tend to favor the mainstream, lacking an inclusive approach toward minority and indigenous communities. These groups are vital members of society and have the right to be included in government initiatives. Unfortunately, this perspective is noticeably absent in government documents.

Jaban., (1980). In her well-known book *"Bangladesh Politics: Problems and Issues,"* examined the political experiences of both Pakistan and Bangladesh discusses twelve articles in which she discusses the crisis of national integration, the independence movement and liberation war, and the challenges faced after independence, such as constitutional experiments, electoral engagement, and political progress. These articles were initially written separately, expressing varied viewpoints, and the issues of political participation are not analyzed in this collection.

Waheduzzaman., (2010). Deals with a study on public involvement in good governance, emphasizing rural development initiatives in Bangladesh. This research examined the local conditions and obstacles that hinder the participation of people in local government entities. By employing a qualitative methodology, the study highlighted issues related to the inefficacy of public involvement. Firstly, none of the stakeholders, including government officials, elected leaders, and community members, recognized the importance of public engagement. Secondly, the avenues for public participation through various management committees were found to be ineffective. Thirdly, there is an absence of a legal framework to guarantee public involvement in rural areas. Lastly, the lack of social capital is obstructing genuine public participation. Additionally, he concluded that the concept of good governance through public involvement, which has been adopted from developed nations via international aid and donor organizations, is somewhat vague and uncertain in a context like Bangladesh.

Azad., (2010). Discusses a small-scale study to investigate the democratic practices adopted by political parties in Bangladesh. He aimed to assess the extent of democracy's functioning within individual political parties in Bangladesh and to evaluate their contribution to reinforcing democracy in the nation. In his analysis, he focused exclusively on the democracy practiced during parliamentary performances and examined it from the view point of the Political parties, regardless of whether they hold power or are in opposition, play a significant role.

Islam, S.M., (2016). "Urban poor and politics in Dhaka: participation, autonomy and dividends." The aim of their research was to understand what defines the politics of the urban poor and how they become involved in political activities. To achieve a comprehensive understanding of the interactions between the poor and politics in Dhaka, they employed an inductive methodology, administering a semi-structured questionnaire via key informant interviews (KII) and focus group discussions (FGDs). The study revealed that long-term slum-dwellers are keen on becoming voters. Furthermore, the urban poor prioritize their daily earnings over engagement in political mobilization.

Chondbury., (1995). Sought to analyze the functioning and nature of constitutional changes in her book *"Constitutional Development in Bangladesh: Stresses and Strains."* She outlined and clarified the main branches of government: the legislature, the executive, and the judiciary. The author examined constitutionalism specifically concerning the legislature during the regimes of Mujib, Zia, and Ershad. She also assessed the interruptions and failures of the democratic process during various periods when the legislature was either completely dismantled or its powers significantly reduced.

In a similar vein, the writer evaluated the executive system in Bangladesh across all four regimes, including periods of martial law in relation to the judiciary. The text highlighted that the absence of an independent judiciary precludes any form of democratic governance, nor can citizens realize their fundamental rights. Her main focus was on the internal political changes achieved through constitutional means. However, in this analysis, the aspect of people's political participation is left unaddressed.

Milbrath., (1965), Examined the central issue of political participation from various perspectives in his book. He explored political participation as influenced by stimuli, individual factors, the political environment, and social status. In summary, the author contends that high levels of participation are not essential for a successful democracy. In fact, he suggests that elevated participation could be harmful to society if it leads to the politicization of a significant portion of social interactions. Nonetheless, the author acknowledges that validating this argument is challenging. Furthermore, it differs across societies and changes over time.

Gugerly, K., (2019). "Oppression, activism, and the political participation of indigenous peoples: a case study in Yucatan, Mexico" deals with that indigenous populations globally tend to experience a greater disparity in political rights, socioeconomic status, and sufficient access to essential resources. Surveys and interviews were conducted to explore potential differences in political attitudes and participation levels between indigenous and non-indigenous individuals. My final assertion is that, in many instances, indigenous groups are likely to engage in political activities at a lower frequency and exhibit more negative feelings towards politics; however, there are certain specific factors in Yucatan that counter this trend of disengagement. These specific factors include low ethnic inequality, minimal political significance of ethnicity, a recent rise in genuine representation, and a distinct sense of pride in their indigenous identity.

Huntington., (1979). In his well-known work "Political Order in Changing Societies," discusses the violence, instability, and disorder found in third-world nations. The author has aimed to illustrate the state of society and to pinpoint the causes of disruption. He qualifies the markers of political order and its absence in this context. He emphasized that economic development is influenced by the relationship between investment and consumption, the presence of political order, the evolution of political institutions, and the integration of emerging social forces into the political arena. In this regard, fostering political participation is crucial for enhancing *political engagement*. However, how political participation can be improved or minimize the gap between politicians and individuals has not been analyzed here.

Research Gap:

No research has been conducted on the political participation of the Koch Community to date and this is the biggest research gap.

The political participation of indigenous peoples in Bangladesh has been subject of many existing studies. Majorities of the studies in Bangladesh were followed descriptive analyses qualitative approaches that are interpreted by the researchers. In addition, the existing studies less focused on the belief systems, cultural norms, motivations and underlying factors that propel the Koch community's political participation. That is why this study will focus on a more thorough understanding on the Koch community's political participation in Bangladesh.

Conclusion:

The various studies that have been done on the political participation of indigenous people of Bangladesh were described and discussed in the section before this one. It is important to majority of studies utilize a qualitative methodology and attempted to explain highlight the phenomenon from the perspective of the researchers. Even the research cited above fell their short in its attempts to comprehend the belief system and the driving forces behind preference for political situation of Koch Community. This study used a qualitative approach to examine the various suspects of Koch community member's political participation situation and offer a thorough understanding of the issue

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